

Design of a Wearable Exoskeleton for Hand Rehabilitation

Mohammad Jabari, Giovanni Colucci, Luigi Tagliavini, Lorenzo Baglieri, Carmen Visconte, Giuseppe Quaglia

Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering (DIMEAS), Politecnico di Torino, Torino, Italy

{mohammad.jabari, giovanni_colucci, luigi.tagliavini, lorenzo.baglieri, carmen.visconte, giuseppe.quaglia}@polito.it

Abstract—Rehabilitation holds significant promise for improving patients' functional abilities through intensive therapy. In recent years, there has been a growing focus on enhancing hand therapy in light of the hand's pivotal role in everyday activities. The paper proposes a novel finger exoskeleton design for hand rehabilitation purposes. This prototype is a part of research that will be used in hand rehabilitation. To minimize mechanical interference with the user's fingers, the exoskeleton employs a remote center of motion mechanism which is manufactured using 3-D printing, making it lightweight and suitable for rehabilitation purposes. Unlike the majority of Remote Joint Mechanisms (RCM) that are meant to be mounted on the dorsal side of each digit, the proposed system is designed to be accommodated entirely within the internal volume of the hand.

Keywords—Finger exoskeleton, Remote center mechanisms, Hand rehabilitation

I. INTRODUCTION

The hand plays a pivotal role in our everyday lives, enabling us to accomplish a variety of essential tasks. Accidents and surgeries, diseases, and strokes in particular can result in the compromise of this vital ability. Individuals with hand disabilities can recover through various therapeutic interventions. Among these approaches, robotic exoskeletons have emerged as effective tools for hand rehabilitation [1]. During this recovery process, engaging interactions between patients and therapeutic devices are essential, which can be facilitated by gaming interfaces. The exoskeleton must possess high levels features in order to accomplish this important task. There are, however, some researchers who have tried to simplify the design in various rehabilitation scenarios, which have proved effective [2].

Exoskeletons for the hands have seen a surge of development over the past decade. Design challenges have been addressed with innovative mechanisms and novel designs. For example, a structure like that one proposed in [3], adopts an open-chained configuration, employing different mechanisms to mitigate interference between digit structures and the exoskeleton mechanism. A number of methods have been proposed to reduce or even eliminate undesirable translational forces on the phalanges, including [4],[5]. Based on [6], incorporating the RCM mechanism minimized these challenges. Moreover, designs such as those shown in [7] can be adjusted to fit different sizes of hands. A common method of implementing remote actuation systems is by means of cable transmission or fluid transmission, reducing the burden on the wearer. A finger, apart from the thumb, represents the most elemental functional unit of the human hand. Fig. 1 (a) illustrates a biomechanical model of a finger, while Fig. 1(b) shows a general view of the proposed finger exoskeleton.

Fig. 1. (a) Biomedical model of finger; (b) CAD model for exoskeleton assembly

A widely accepted biomechanical model of a finger consists of four sequentially linked components: a fixed metacarpal, proximal phalanx, middle phalanx, and distal phalanx. Revolute joints connect these links to each other. Due to the fact that the distal interphalangeal (DIP) joint does not play a critical role in hand rehabilitation, this study introduces a meticulously designed RCM exoskeleton joint developed specifically for the proximal interphalangeal (PIP) and metacarpophalangeal (MCP) joints. In addition, it is noteworthy that most research endeavours assume idealized revolute behaviour for each joint. Nevertheless, real joints do not exhibit flawless revolute motion. They have imperfections such as friction and sliding. Consequently, actual models need mechanisms to handle these imperfections.

An innovative finger exoskeleton design is presented in this paper that meets specific requirements:

- Make sure the finger fits seamlessly and is interference-free
- Adapts to various finger sizes and covers an acceptable range of motion (ROM)
- Each joint can be individually actuated
- This mechanism can be mounted on the palm of the hand instead of the dorsal side

The paper unfolds in three sections: conceptual design, prototype development, and concluding insights. Only the mechanism is described, the actuation and sensing systems are under development and will be presented in subsequent works.

II. CONCEPTUAL DESIGN

A. Technical considerations

The design of the prototype for rehabilitation of the flexion-extension movement of the fingers is based on the configuration of the parallel exoskeleton model. It was necessary to measure a volunteer in order to design the first prototype. Using a vernier caliper, measurements were performed on phalanges. Table 1 records these measurements.

B. Joint Mechanism

The mechanism joints were modelled as RCM, meaning that the exoskeleton can track finger movement without mechanical interference. The RCM allows the main links to have movement equidistant to the user finger phalanx, in contrast to modelling the mechanism joint as a simple revolute joint. As shown in Fig 2, revolute joints are denoted by the letters A through K, and links by the numbers 1 through 4.

III. MANUFACTURE AND ASSEMBLY

Assuming the parameters $L_1=36$ mm, $L_2=23$ mm, and $\alpha=40^\circ$ are set, a first prototype was developed to test the preliminary concept of motion as well as the overall structure (see Fig 2). As a result of the obtained dimensions (TABLE I) and a 20 mm finger width, three-dimensional models were developed with a 2mm wall thickness to represent finger exoskeletons. The PIP and MCP for index and ring finger had similar geometries, while the PIP supported the fingertip. The procedure has been followed for the other fingers as well.

The prototype is made of tough PLA through additive manufacturing techniques. The selection of proper design parameters is fundamental for following the finger's motion throughout the ROM without impeding configuration or sliding problems, as shown in Fig.3.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, we introduced an exoskeleton finger incorporating RCM Joint Mechanisms designed for hand rehabilitation purposes. Our prototype demonstrates a seamless and natural finger movement without requiring additional actuation effort. Notably, the design prioritizes user comfort, eliminating translational forces and sliding issues in

TABLE I. Parameter for subjects' fingers (units: mm)

Finger parameters	Index Finger	Middle Finger	Ring Finger	Little Finger
Proximal phalanx	46	47	46	39
Middle phalanx	27	28	27	24

Fig. 2. Schematic view of the exoskeleton mechanism

Fig. 3. Sequence of movement of the prototype corresponding with the finger

the phalanges during natural finger movements. The prototype was first tested on a limited number of people as a first experimental result. Currently, we are working on providing the prototype with adjustable stiffness for passive rehabilitation applications. In our future research, we intend to explore the integration of pneumatic systems to control the stiffness of grasping manipulation, and sensors for monitoring rehabilitation activities.

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